

Full Research Paper

Mapping the user co-creation approaches in Living labs to the research, development, and innovation processes for human-centric innovation

Authors

Fumiya Akasaka¹, Yui Murakami¹, Kentaro Watanabe¹

¹ Research Institute on Human and Societal Augmentation (RIHSA), National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), Japan

Abstract

One important role of Living Labs (LLs) is to support research, development and innovation (RDI) processes. Previous LL studies have strongly emphasised the importance of user co-creation in supporting RDI projects. In addition, scholars have suggested that user co-creation in LLs involves various approaches. However, previous studies have not systematically presented categories of user co-creation approaches in LLs and their relationships with the phases of the RDI process. Co-creation in LLs therefore remains an ambiguous concept; it is often treated as a ‘magic word’ that can solve all difficulties in the co-creative RDI process. This lack of a deep understanding of the co-creation concept in LLs makes it difficult to plan effective integration of user co-creation approaches into the entire RDI process for human-centric innovation. Therefore, through a case study, this study aims to clarify how user co-creation approaches in LLs can be integrated into the RDI process. To this end, we first identify the categories of user co-creation approaches promoted in LLs to support RDI projects. Then, we clarify the relationship between user co-creation approaches and the RDI process in the context of human-centric innovation.

Key words

User co-creation, RDI, human-centric innovation, case study

Introduction

Living Labs (LLs) have attracted attention as an approach for promoting human-centric innovations through long-term co-creation with users and various stakeholders (Yasuoka, Akasaka, Kimura, & Ihara, 2018). Scholars have suggested that LLs encompass diverse types, such as those focusing on urban problem solving, rural innovations, technology validation, new solution development, networking for innovation, and knowledge sharing among various stakeholders (Cascone, Scuderi, Guarnaccia, & Timpanaro, 2024; Hossain, Leminen, & Westerlund, 2019; Schuurman, Mar, De Marez, & Ballon, 2015). One important role of LLs that is commonly found in such diverse types is to support the research, development, and innovation (RDI) process, which aims to integrate research and (experimental) development (i.e. R&D) and innovation activities for the social implementation of technologies (Akasaka, Mitake, Oura, Watanabe, & Kojima, 2023). Thus, LLs are a major focus of Horizon2020, which is a large-scale RDI program in the EU (Compagnucci, Spigarelli, Coelho, & Duarte, 2021).

Previous LL studies have strongly emphasised the importance of ‘user co-creation’ in supporting the RDI process. User co-creation has been considered useful, for example, in fitting technology and solutions to user needs and local problems (Ståhlbröst, 2008), considering the cultural and social background behind problems (Von Geibler et al., 2014), obtaining and integrating users’ knowledge and opinions in innovation ideas (Schuurman, De Marez, & Ballon, 2015), and promoting changes in citizens’ behaviour and lifestyles towards social transformation (Voytenko, McCormick, Evans, & Schliwa, 2016). Scholars have also suggested that user co-creation in LLs includes various approaches carried out in various phases of the RDI process with different objectives, such as co-creation for problem exploration, idea generation, and prototyping. However, previous studies have not presented systematic knowledge of user co-creation approaches in LLs to support RDI projects. Specifically, they have not systematically clarified the categories of user co-creation approaches in LLs and their relationships with the phases of the RDI process. Thus, co-creation in LLs remains an ambiguous concept; it is often treated as a ‘magic word’ (Puerari et al., 2018) that can solve all the difficulties in the co-creative RDI process. This lack of a deep understanding of the co-creation concept in LLs makes it difficult to plan effective integration of user co-creation approaches into the entire RDI process for human-centric innovation.

Therefore, this study aims to clarify how user co-creation approaches in LLs can be integrated into the RDI process. To this end, through a case study, we first identify the

categories of user co-creation approaches promoted by LLs to support RDI projects. Then, we clarify the relationship between user co-creation approaches and the RDI process in the context of human-centric innovation. This study addresses the following two research questions (RQs):

RQ1: What user co-creation approaches are promoted in LLs to support RDI projects? How can they be categorised?

RQ2: How can the various user co-creation approaches be mapped to the phases of the RDI process?

Theoretical background

RDI

According to the OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development), the concept of R&D is defined as ‘creative and systematic work undertaken in order to increase the stock of knowledge’. It covers three types of activity: basic research, applied research, and experimental development (OECD, 2015). Meanwhile, RDI is a broader concept than R&D, with the addition of ‘I’, namely innovation. Innovation is defined as ‘the introduction of new products or services to the market’ (Schumpeter & Swedberg, 2021); it refers to activities aimed at the social implementation and dissemination of new technologies, products, or services. Thus, RDI corresponds to a long-term process that encompasses a wide range of activities, from basic research to technological development, product/service development, and the social implementation and dissemination of the products/services. Research institutions and corporate research departments have recently been required to engage in RDI rather than traditional R&D, as there has been a strong social demand for innovations to solve social problems.

Research, development, demonstration, and deployment (RDD&D), which originally developed by the Department of Energy in the US (US Department of Energy, n.d.), is a similar concept to RDI. It is an extended R&D activity model that emphasises technology transfer to the market. It comprises four phases: basic research (R), technology and technology-based product development (first D), demonstration of prototypes and products (second D), and business deployment (third D).

In systems engineering, the technology readiness level (TRL) was developed as an indicator to evaluate the achievement of activities that incorporate technical ideas into new products or systems (Olechowski, Eppinger, Joglekar, & Tomaschek, 2020). It

evaluates the process starting with technology in a basic theoretical form and progressing to a system proven in a used environment using a nine-level scale (Olechowski et al., 2020). Although the TRL was originally developed to manage projects for large-scale physical systems, it has been modified for application in RDI projects in various fields. For example, in Horizon2020, the nine levels of TRL are defined as: (1) basic principles observed, (2) technology concept formulated, (3) experimental proof of concept, (4) technology validated in lab, (5) technology validated in relevant environment, (6) technology demonstrated in relevant environment, (7) system prototype demonstration in operational environment, (8) system complete and qualified, and (9) actual system proven in operational environment (Apré, 2022).

Design approaches for human-centric innovation

Many scholars have strongly criticised the technology-centric approach to innovation in the context of RDI. Therefore, a human-centric approach is important to realise innovation in a sustainable and well-being society (Hollands, 2015; Trencher, 2019). Against this backdrop, design approaches such as human-centred design (HCD) (Cooper, 1999; Gill, 1991; Norman, 1990), design thinking (DT) (Brown, 2008), and service design (SD) (Stickdorn & Schneider, 2012; Zomerdijk & Voss, 2010) have attracted considerable attention for facilitating human-centric innovation. A common feature of these design approaches is the involvement of users in the early stages of the design process. Furthermore, all approaches commonly include iterative processes comprising exploration (i.e. exploring users' problems and needs through observation and interviews), creation (i.e. ideating solutions and creating prototypes), and evaluation (i.e. evaluating prototypes through user tests). This design approach is currently widely accepted by many universities and research institutions and often applied to the innovation process of RDI.

User co-creation in LLs

In Europe in particular, LLs are positioned as infrastructures to support RDI initiatives. Previous studies have proposed the concept of 'LL as a Service', which views an LL as a service that supports RDI activities such as technological validation, user testing, and concept creation, in small- and medium-sized enterprises, research institutions, and public institutions (Grotenhuis, 2017; Ståhlbröst, 2013). Scholars have analysed and organised portfolios of such services and value propositions that LL can provide to clients (Santonen et al., 2024).

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures:

Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

One of the most important methodological features of LLs is the integration of ‘co-creation’ into the RDI process. Co-creation in this context includes two types: co-creation with users (or user co-creation) and co-creation with diverse stakeholders. The term stakeholders in this context covers the four actors mentioned in the quadruple helix model (QHM): industry, government, academia, and citizens (Baccarne, Logghe, Schuurman, & De Marez, 2016; Nguyen & Marques, 2022). As stated by Schuurman et al. (2015), the theoretical background of the former co-creation corresponds to ‘user innovation’ (Von Hippel, 1986), and ‘participatory design’ (Simonsen & Robertson, 2013), and the latter to ‘open innovation’ (Chesbrough & Appleyard, 2007). Although both types of co-creation are core methodological features of LLs, continuous user participation and co-creation are important for differentiating LLs from other approaches (Almirall, Lee, & Wareham, 2012). Therefore, this study focuses on ‘user co-creation’ in LLs.

Previous LL studies have investigated and analysed means of effectively promoting user co-creation in LLs. For example, Soini et al. analysed the impact of contexts surrounding LLs on co-creation activities through a case study of LLs in rural areas (Soini et al., 2023). Menny et al. clarified the user roles in co-creation in LLs (Menny, Palgan, & McCormick, 2018). Puerari et al. analysed how co-creation have been promoted in LLs and classified co-creation approaches based on five perspectives: (1) purpose, (2) formal and informal co-creation, (3) ownership, (4) motivation and incentives, and (5) space/place (Puerari et al., 2018). Haug and Mergel analysed the contextual factors that lead to successful co-creation in LLs (Haug & Mergel, 2021). Franz et al. investigated co-creation in the urban LL context to discuss how urban LLs are designed and planned (Franz, Tausz, & Thiel, 2015). Massari et al. conducted a detailed literature review on the concept of co-creation and discussed the importance of creativity (Massari, Galli, Mattioni, & Chiffolleau, 2023).

Although many previous studies have discussed user co-creation in LLs, none have systematically analysed the relationship between user co-creation and the RDI process. While user co-creation in LLs includes various approaches (Puerari et al., 2018), it has not been clarified which user co-creation approaches should be utilised according to the different phases and purposes of RDI projects. This makes it difficult to plan how to integrate user co-creation approaches within the entire RDI process aimed at human-centric innovation. Furthermore, this has led to the current situation in which the value of LLs for the effective promotion of RDI projects is being discussed in a scattered manner and has not been clarified systematically.

Method

Overview

This study aims to clarify how user co-creation approaches in LLs can be integrated into the RDI process. To this end, we adopt the qualitative case study approach (Merriam, 1998; Yin, 1994). An overview of the analytical process is presented in Figure 1. We first selected cases of LLs that support RDI projects and collected data regarding their RDI process from multiple sources (e.g. interviews with LL organisers, project reports, and papers). We extracted specific activities from the data for co-creation that include interactions with users or citizens. We then analysed the extracted activities by coding them from the viewpoint of the RDI process to identify the categories of user co-creation activities in LLs. Finally, we mapped these categories to the RDI process to clarify their relationships. The remainder of this section explains the details of the case selection and data collection, the RDI process model used for coding tags, and the coding process.

Figure 1. Overview of the analysis process

Case selection and data collection

We selected the cases for analysis based on the purposeful sampling approach (Palinkas et al., 2015). Specifically, we selected four LL cases promoted in Japan that strongly fit the context of this study, that is, ‘LLs to support RDI projects for human-centric innovation’. An overview of the selected cases is provided in Table 1. Living Labs include two layers: projects and platforms (Suurman, 2015; Akasaka et al., 2025). Living labs as projects refer to co-creation projects aimed at achieving specific goals. Living labs as platforms refer to institutional platforms that supports various co-creation projects. In this study, we selected Living labs as platforms that include one or more co-creation projects to support RDI initiatives.

Regarding three (A, B, and C) of the four cases selected, no reports or papers depicting details of their LLs and RDI processes have been published. Thus, we conducted in-depth interviews with LL organisers and stakeholders involved in LL operations. The interviews were conducted using the semi-structured interview approach (Barriball & While, 1994). We asked about the details of the project’s purpose, the entire RDI process, and the co-creation activities with users and the citizen community. The interview data were transcribed for analysis. Meanwhile, in Case D, one of the authors was deeply involved in the management and operation of LLs. Thus, to account for the RDI process and specific activities for user co-creation comprehensively, we conducted a review to reflect and list the activities promoted in the projects. In this reflection process, we also used reports and documents (e.g. presentation materials) that depict the detailed process of the projects and their processes as supplementary data sources.

Table 1. Selected LL cases

Case	Theme	Detailed description
A	Health-care	<p>A living lab established for supporting a large-scale RDI project in medical and healthcare field. The lab is in a corner of a shopping centre that many residents use in their daily lives.</p> <p>Various devices for measuring biological data and health status are equipped in the lab; anyone can use them with the staff’s support.</p> <p>Medical experts come to the lab weekly, and people can measure the precise data on their health status under the guidance of the experts. The collected data are used for basic research, such as developing algorithms for estimating disease risk, with the consent of participants.</p> <p>The lab displays various information related to disease prevention, aiming to foster awareness and a culture of disease prevention.</p>
B	Local problem solving (rural area)	<p>An urban living lab operated in a countryside area in Japan where ageing has been particularly advancing. Various topics such as local transportation, health care, and community revitalization are focused as important challenges in the lab.</p> <p>Especially, an RDI project to develop a transportation service using personal mobility vehicles has been promoted to solve local transportation issues.</p> <p>To date, the living lab has held frequent discussions with the local community to develop a prototype of a transportation service using personal mobility vehicles. In addition, some social experiments to evaluate the developed service have been conducted.</p>
C	Local problem solving (urban context)	<p>An urban living lab located in a waterfront area where various companies are gathered.</p> <p>With the shared goal of solving social issues in the area, the lab aims to promote co-creation among diverse stakeholders, including companies, universities, government, and citizens.</p> <p>Currently, various activities to build co-creation relationships between companies and citizens are being carried out. However, specific activities for technology, product, and service co-creation have not yet been implemented.</p>
D	Local problem solving (smart city)	<p>An urban living lab operated in a smart city in Japan. Several co-creation projects that aim at solving local issues, have been implemented. In this analysis, we especially focused on two projects: a project aimed at solving regional mobility issues and a project to develop cutting-edge sensing technology and smart home services that utilise such technology.</p> <p>In the mobility project, a solution, which includes a digital signage service for real-time sharing of public transportation information, autonomous robots for automatic delivery from supermarkets to residential areas, and a sharing service of personal mobility vehicles, was co-designed and tested through social experiments.</p> <p>In the smart home project, some societal visions for ideal ageing was developed with citizens and smart home service concepts that realise the visions have also been created. Based on the service concepts, actual devices and working prototypes of smart home services have been developed. User evaluations of the developed smart home prototypes have also been conducted.</p>

RDI process model

In this study, we analysed the relationship between user co-creation activities and the RDI process. However, no unified model representing the RDI process for human-centric innovation has been established to date. Therefore, for the analysis, we developed an RDI process model focusing on the human-centric innovation context based on the previous studies described in Sections 2.1 and 2.2.

The developed RDI process model is illustrated in Figure 2. This model comprised four main phases: basic research, product/technology-level (PT-level) development, service system-level (SS-level) development, and deployment. These four phases were identified by summarising existing related models, such as RDI, RDD&D, and TRL. Furthermore, according to the design approaches for human-centric innovation (i.e. HCD, DT, and SD described in Section 2.2), the two main phases of development (PT- and SS-level development) were divided into three sub-phases: exploration, creation, and evaluation. Here, ‘exploration’ corresponds to the activities for user observation, need identification, and problem definition; ‘creation’ includes activities for ideation, concept generation, and prototyping; and ‘evaluation’ refers to prototype evaluation, user tests, and experiments in the use environment. Consequently, the developed RDI process model was composed of eight phases: (1) basic research, (2) PT-level exploration, (3) PT-level creation, (4) PT-level evaluation, (5) SS-level exploration, (6) SS-level creation, (7) SS-level evaluation, and (8) deployment. The correspondences between these eight phases and the existing related models (i.e. RDI, RDD&D, TRL, HCD, DT, and SD) are shown in Table 2. In this study, these eight phases were used as coding tags when analysing the activities for user co-creation in LLs.

Figure 2. RDI process model used for the analysis

Coding process

In this study, we first extracted the activities for user co-creation implemented in each LL case. We comprehensively extracted activities that included interactions and communication with users and citizens (i.e. potential users) as well as direct co-creation

activities, such as user-participatory workshops. The extracted activities were then analysed through a two-step coding process. In the first step, we coded the extracted activities using the eight phases of the RDI process model described in Section 3.3. In this step, activities that were not coded to any phases were simply tagged as ‘unclassified’. In the second step, the tagged results were further categorised into sub-groups based on the content and meaning of the activities. Through this process, we obtained categories of user co-creation activities in LLs.

Table 2. Correspondence between the developed RDI process model and existing models

	RDI	RDD&D	TRL	HCD	DT	SD
Basic research	Research	Research	1. Basic principles observed	-	-	
PT-level exploration	Development	Development	2. Technology concept formulated 3. Experimental proof of concept	Understand and specify the context of use	Empathize	
PT-level creation			4. Technology validated in lab 5. Technology validated in relevant environment 6. Technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Specify the user and organizational requirements Produce design solution	Define Ideate Prototype	-
PT-level evaluation				Evaluate designs against requirements	Test	
SS-level exploration		Demonstration	7. System prototype demonstration in operational environment	Understand and specify the context of use	Empathize	Exploration
SS-level creation			8. System complete and qualified 9. Actual system proven in operational environment	Specify the user and organizational requirements Produce design solution	Define Ideate Prototype	Creation
SS-level evaluation				Evaluate designs against requirements	Test	Reflection
Deployment	Innovation	Deployment	-	-	-	Implementation

Results

Identifying the categories of user co-creation activities in LLs

Figure 3 shows the partial results of the activity extraction and coding processes. Through this analysis, we identified 11 categories of user co-creation activities in LLs. Table 3 presents the identified categories and their details. The identified categories included various types of user co-creation activities, from basic research to innovation phases. For example, the category of user co-creation activities ‘collecting living data for research’

(ID1) relates to basic research; the categories ‘concept co-creation’ (ID3) and ‘co-visioning’ (ID4) correspond to the development phase, and ‘implementation planning’ (ID7) relates to the deployment phase. As shown in the ‘User roles’ column in Table 3, the roles of users and levels of their engagement were also varied according to the activity categories.

Interestingly, the categories also included activities related to the preparation for the co-creation, such as ‘networking’ (ID9), ‘knowledge sharing’ (ID10), and ‘training’ (ID11). These are preparatory activities to build foundational relationships and basic knowledge or skills for effective co-creation with users. While these activities are not directly related to user co-creation in the RDI context, they are important for enhancing the effectiveness of user co-creation. These activities are also referred to as ‘backstage’ activities in community-based co-design studies (Le Dantec & Fox, 2015).

Figure 3. Part of the analysis results (activity extraction and two-step coding)

Mapping the user co-creation activities to the RDI process model

In the first step of the coding process, several activities were tagged as ‘Unclassified’; this result indicated that the pre-defined RDI process (see Figure 2) did not cover RDI phases corresponding to all identified user co-creation activities. Therefore, we extended

the RDI process model for the mapping analysis between user co-creation activities and the RDI process.

Figure 4 shows the extended RDI process model used in the mapping analysis. Five phases were added to the model (orange in Figure 4): social system-level (SoS-level) exploration, SoS-level creation, SoS-level evaluation, intervention for social transition, and preparation for co-creation. The first three phases (SoS-level exploration, creation, and evaluation) can be grouped as those related to social system-level development. These correspond to the 'D' in the entire RDI process with a focus on the social system level, which was not mentioned in the pre-defined RDI process model. Meanwhile, 'intervention for social transition' refers to activities to realise the transition of the social system, including the transitions of citizens' mindsets, behaviours, customs, and culture, which are significant for realising human-centric innovation. This transition of social systems goes beyond simply deploying and disseminating new products and services in society; it requires continuous and long-term interventions in people's lives and society (Irwin, 2015). Thus, we added this as an additional phase, separately from 'deployment'. The fifth phase, 'preparation for co-creation', includes preparation activities for relationship building and networking with users. These preparatory activities are conducted both 'before' and 'during' RDI projects as backstage activities to enable better co-creation. Therefore, in Figure 4, it is located 'before' (left) and 'below' the main RDI process.

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

Table 3. 11 identified categories of user co-creation activities in LLs

ID	Module	Description	Examples	User roles
1	Collecting living data for research	Facilitating the participation of people (potential users) in collecting data on their physical and psychological states, behaviours, and environment in their daily lives. The collected data are used in basic research conducted in research institutes and companies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data acquisition at a lab set up in living environments (e.g. a shopping centre) Participation of local residents in experiments and surveys for basic research 	Information
2	Collecting users' voices	Facilitating the participation of users in collecting data on users' voices (e.g., opinions and ideas) through interviews and questionnaires. The collected data are mainly used as input for projects that have specific target, such as solving local issues and developing technology/services.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A web survey to investigate and analyse regional issues User interviews to explore problems to be solved 	Information; Consultation
3	Concept co-creation	Facilitating collaboration with users in creating concepts of technology, products, and services, or improve the concepts based on feedback from users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-design workshop with users for creating concepts of technology, products, or services User interviews to obtain feedback on the concepts created 	Consultation; Co-creation
4	Co-visioning	Facilitating collaboration with users in creating visions of the desired society in the future.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-design workshop with users for creating visions of future society User interviews to obtain feedback on the visions created 	Consultation; Co-creation
5	Technology validation	Facilitating the participation of users in validating the developed technology (e.g. functionality, performance, and user acceptance).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User test (product/technology-level) Experiments in living environments (product/technology-level) 	Information; Consultation
6	Service system (SeS) evaluation	Facilitating the participation of users in evaluating the developed service system (e.g. usefulness for users, business viability, and operability).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User test (service system-level) Experiments in living environments (service system-level) 	Information; Consultation
7	Implementation planning	Facilitating collaboration with users in developing plans for the implementation and dissemination of developed technologies, products, or services, considering the local resources, situations, and constraints in the living environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussion with users to develop plans for the implementation within the constraints of the field 	Consultation; Co-creation
8	Cultural development	Promoting user-participatory events (e.g. hands-on events, social experiments, science communication) for fostering their understanding of new social systems, services, and technologies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exhibition of future services at a lab in living environment Hands-on events to raise awareness and understanding of new products Science communication sessions to residents 	Co-creation
9	Networking	Building connections and relationships with people and organisations related to geographical areas and areas of interest. This activities are mainly aimed at future collaboration with users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuous communication with local residents and organisations 	(Backstage)
10	Knowledge sharing	Organising lectures or seminars to provide opportunities to learn basic knowledge about social issues addressed in the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lectures and discussions on a specific social problem 	(Backstage)
11	Training	Providing opportunities for developers and researchers to experience communication and collaboration with users to learn the mindset and skills necessary for co-creation with users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dialogue meetings between users and researchers 	(Backstage)

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

This extended RDI process forms a two-dimensional structure comprising two axes: the RDI flow from upstream to downstream (i.e. research, development, and innovation) and the system level from concrete to abstract (i.e. the PT, SeS, and SoS levels).

Figure 4. Extended RDI process model

We mapped the identified categories of user co-creation activities (Table 3) to the extended RDI process model (Figure 4). This mapping was conducted based on the results of the coding analysis described in Section 4.1. The results are shown in Figure 5. The 11 identified categories were mapped across the broad coverage of the extended RDI process model. The mapping results clearly show how various user co-creation activities in LLs are conducted in different phases and at different system levels throughout the entire RDI process.

Figure 5. Results of mapping the user co-creation activities to the extended RDI process model

This diagram is an important deliverable of this study and clarifies the relationships between user co-creation activities in LLs and the RDI process for human-centric innovation. From this mapped diagram, LL practitioners and managers can easily and clearly capture user co-creation activities that can be applied to support the different phases of the entire RDI process. This supports the planning and design of a co-creative RDI process that integrates LL approaches.

Discussion

Theoretical contributions

Although previous LL studies have strongly emphasised the importance of user co-creation, it remains an ambiguous concept in LLs. In particular, the systematic knowledge of the effective integration of user co-creation approaches into the RDI process has not been clarified. In response to this, this study identified 11 categories of user co-creation activities through an in-depth case analysis. Presenting the structured and categorised components of user co-creation approaches in LLs helps LL practitioners and researchers to gain a clearer and deeper understanding of the ambiguous concept of user co-creation in LLs. In addition, we mapped the identified categories of user co-creation into the RDI process model. The diagram obtained through the mapping analysis can also be regarded as knowledge that presents how user co-creation approaches can be integrated and contribute to the RDI process for human-centric innovation. Therefore, the identified categories and mapping results are important theoretical contributions of this study that enhance the existing knowledge of user co-creation in LLs.

This study also contributes to discussions on the RDI process model that integrates the LL approach. In this study, we extended the RDI process model based on the interview results. Previous LL studies have mainly focused on the development (D) and innovation (I) phases of RDI. For example, Menny et al. (2018) focused on the process comprising design, implementation, and evaluation of innovations in their analysis of urban LLs, which means that they focused little on the basic research phase. In the RDI process developed in the Horizon2020 VITALISE project, the research (R) phase corresponds to ‘design research’ for creating solutions rather than ‘basic research’; this also indicates that their emphasis was placed more on the development (D)- and innovation (I)-related phases (Petronikolou et al., 2024). In contrast, the RDI process model developed in this study covers a wider range of phases, from basic research to innovation activities. Furthermore, the developed model also covers a wide range of system levels, from PT to SoS. The emphasis on the SoS level, which was added in this study, resonates with transition

design (Irwin, 2015), which is a design methodology for social transformation proposed in the design study field. Transition design includes steps for vision design and continuous intervention for social-level changes. The RDI process model developed in this study also includes corresponding activities with such steps: ‘co-visioning’ (ID4) and ‘cultural development’ (ID8). Therefore, the identified RDI process model can be viewed as an integrated model that extends existing RDI-related models (RDD&D, TRL, SD, and DT) by adding the transition design approach. This model is considered to fit the context of RDI projects supported by LL approaches strongly. This is because, as emphasised in previous studies, one of the strengths of LLs for realising innovation is their capability to realise social transformation, including a change in people’s mindsets beyond simply realising technological innovation (Voytenko et al., 2016). Based on these discussions, we conclude that the developed RDI process model theoretically contributes to the LL research community, as it can serve as a foundational framework for discussing LL-supported RDI processes for human-centric and social innovations.

Practical contributions

For human-centric innovation, it is important to involve users in the various phases of the RDI process to reflect their opinions and ideas (Adreani, Kalchschmidt, Pinto, & Sayegh, 2019). Thus, RDI project managers must plan and design methods to integrate the user co-creation approach into the entire RDI process according to the objectives and circumstances of their project. However, planning the effective integration of user co-creation activities is generally difficult, as user co-creation approaches are diverse and few guidelines to support the planning work exist (Akasaka, Mitake, Watanabe, & Shimomura, 2022).

This study provides findings that are useful for such managerial issues. Specifically, the 11 identified categories and mapping results can serve as ‘building blocks’ for designing both project-level and platform-level living labs. Regarding the design of project-level living labs, project managers can consider how to integrate user co-creation activities into their RDI process by selecting, combining, and customising the presented categories of user co-creation activities. Meanwhile, regarding the platform-level living labs, living lab manager can plan what living lab services should be prepared and provided to support co-creation projects in the living lab. As such the identified categories of user co-creation activities can function as the ‘design pattern’ (Mayvan, Rasoolzadegan, & Yazdi, 2017) that supports the configuration of project- and platform-level living labs. Although this study does not provide specific procedures for utilising this design pattern, we believe

that it is practically useful in providing fundamental knowledge for planning, improving, and modifying RDI processes supported by the LL approach.

Limitations

This study has the following limitations.

- This study only focused on analysis of co-creation with users. However, as mentioned in Section 2.3, living labs adopt a co-creation approach based on QHM, which involves complex co-creation among users, companies, government, and academia. The lack of analysis of this kind of complex co-creation process among diverse stakeholders is one of the limitations of this study and a topic to be addressed in future research.
- The cases collected in this study were only Japanese; thus, the geographical scope of data collection was limited. Therefore, we must analyse cases in other geographical areas to verify the generalisability of our findings.
- The validity of the findings (i.e. the 11 categories of user co-creation and mapping results to the RDI process) was not sufficiently evaluated. Therefore, future work should include expert reviews by professionals in the LL and RDI fields.
- Regarding the first point, many Japanese LLs are still in the early stages of RDI, meaning that there are few cases that focus on the I in RDI, that is, the phase of social implementation of technologies, products, and services. Therefore, we should analyse how user co-creation approaches can be integrated into the process of socialising technologies, products, and services. For this purpose, focusing on cases in Europe, where the use of living laboratories is mature, will be useful.
- In Section 5.2, we argued that the 11 identified categories can be used as design patterns to support RDI managers in planning the RDI process. However, this study did not develop concrete processes (e.g. step-by-step processes) or practical tools for supporting RDI managers. To realise the utilisation of the findings of this study by practitioners, we will develop practical tools (e.g. guidelines and design cards (Roy & Warren, 2019)) to support the planning and design of LL-supported RDI processes.

Conclusions and outlook

This study aimed to clarify how user co-creation approaches in LLs can be integrated into the RDI process for human-centric innovation. Specifically, we addressed the following two RQs:

RQ1: What user co-creation approaches are promoted in LLs to support RDI projects? How can they be categorised?

RQ2: How can the various user co-creation approaches be mapped to the phases of the RDI process?

For RQ1, using a case study approach, we identified 11 categories of user co-creation activities in LLs to support RDI projects. The concept of user co-creation in LLs has been vaguely captured in previous studies; thus, the findings of this study will help to gain a more concrete and deeper understanding of user co-creation approaches in LLs. For RQ2, we clarified the relationships between the categories of user co-creation and the RDI processes. Specifically, we mapped the identified categories of user co-creation activities into the phases of the RDI process. These mapping results can support RDI managers in planning the user co-creative RDI process, as they provide foundational knowledge on how to integrate user co-creation approaches into RDI projects for human-centric innovation.

Future studies will include verification of the broader applicability of the findings of this study by analysing LL cases in broader contexts and conducting expert reviews. In addition, we will develop concrete processes (e.g. step-by-step processes) and practical tools to support RDI managers based on the findings. This will be practically important for accelerating the utilisation of the findings of this study.

Acknowledgement

We express our gratitude to the interviewees for their support. This study was supported by the Toyota Foundation D22-ST-0013 (Project Name: ‘Infrastructuring Living Labs: Building Infrastructure to Support Living Lab Practices’) and JST, Grant Number JPMJPF2115.

References

1. Akasaka, F., Mitake, Y., Oura, F., Watanabe, K., & Kojima, H. (2023). Infrastructuring social labs: Establishing a sustainable research, development, and innovation platform driven by citizen collaboration, In Proc. Open Living Lab Days 2023, Barcelona, Spain.
2. Akasaka, F., Mitake, Y., Watanabe, K., & Shimomura, Y. (2022). A framework for 'configuring participation' in living labs. *Design Science*, 8, e28. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dsj.2022.22>
3. Akasaka, F., Yasuoka, M., Nakatani, M., Akiyama, H., & Nambu, R. (2025). Development of a Tool to Support the Sustainable Management of Urban Living Labs as Platforms for Co-Creation. *Sustainability*, 17(10), 4357. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17104357>
4. Almirall, E., Lee, M., & Wareham, J. (2012). Mapping living labs in the landscape of innovation methodologies. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 2(9).
5. Andreani, S., Kalchschmidt, M., Pinto, R., & Sayegh, A. (2019). Reframing technologically enhanced urban scenarios: A design research model towards human centered smart cities. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 142, 15–25.
6. Apre, C. (2022). Guiding notes to use the TRL self-assessment tool. NCP Portal Management. <https://horizoneuropencppportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-12/trl-assessment-tool-guide-final.pdf>
7. Baccarne, B., Logghe, S., Schuurman, D., & De Marez, L. (2016). Governing quintuple helix innovation: urban living labs and socio-ecological entrepreneurship. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 6(3), 22–30.
8. Barriball, K. L., & While, A. (1994) Collecting data using a semi-structured interview: a discussion paper, *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 19(2), 328–335.
9. Brown, T. (2008). Design thinking. *Harvard Business Review*, 86(6), 84, 1-10.
10. Cascone, G., Scuderi, A., Guarnaccia, P., & Timpanaro, G. (2024). Promoting innovations in agriculture: Living labs in the development of rural areas. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 443, 141247.
11. Chesbrough, H. W., & Appleyard, M. M. (2007). Open innovation and strategy. *California Management Review*, 50(1), 57–76.
12. Compagnucci, L., Spigarelli, F., Coelho, J., & Duarte, C. (2021). Living Labs and user engagement for innovation and sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289, 125721.
13. Cooper, A. (1999). *The Inmates Are Running the Asylum: Why High-Tech Products Drive Us Crazy and How To Restore The Sanity*, Sams Publishing, Indianapolis, Indiana.
14. Franz, Y., Tausz, K., & Thiel, S. K. (2015). Contextuality and co-creation matter: A qualitative case study comparison of living lab concepts in urban research. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 5(12), 48-55.
15. Gill, K. S. (1991). Summary Of Human-Centred Systems Research In Europe, Part 1. *Systemist*, 13(1) 7–27.
16. Grotenhuis, F. D. (2017). Living labs as service providers: From proliferation to coordination. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 36(4), 52–57.
17. Haug, N., & Mergel, I. (2021). Public Value Co-Creation in Living Labs—Results from Three Case Studies. *Administrative Sciences*, 11(3), 74.
18. Hollands, R. G. (2015). Critical interventions into the corporate smart city. *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society*, 8(1), 61–77.
19. Hossain, M., Leminen, S., & Westerlund, M. (2019). A systematic review of living lab literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 213, 976–988.
20. Irwin, T. (2015). Transition design: A proposal for a new area of design practice, study, and research. *Design and Culture*, 7(2), 229–246.
21. Soini, K., Anderson, C. C., Polderman, A., Teresa, C., Sisay, D., Kumar, P., ..., & Heikki Tuomenvirt. (2023). Context matters: Co-creating nature-based solutions in rural living labs, *Land Use Policy*, 133, 106839.
22. Le Dantec, C. A., & Fox, S. (2015). Strangers at the gate: Gaining access, building rapport, and co-constructing community-based research. In Proc. 18th ACM Conference on Computer Supported

- Cooperative Work & Social Computing, pp. 1348–1358, Vancouver, Canada.
23. Massari, S., Galli, F., Mattioni, D., & Chiffolleau, Y. (2023). Co-creativity in living labs: Fostering creativity in co-creation processes to transform food systems. *Journal of Science Communication*, 22(3), A03.
 24. Mayvan, B. B., Rasoolzadegan, A., & Yazdi, Z. G. (2017). The state of the art on design patterns: A systematic mapping of the literature. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 125, 93–118.
 25. Menny, M., Palgan, Y. V., & McCormick, K. (2018). Urban living labs and the role of users in co-creation. *GAIA - Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 27(1), 68–77.
 26. Merriam, S. B. (1998). *Qualitative research and case study applications in education*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
 27. Nguyen, H. T., & Marques, P. (2022). The promise of living labs to the Quadruple Helix stakeholders: Exploring the sources of (dis)satisfaction. *European Planning Studies*, 30(6), 1124–1143.
 28. Norman, D. A. (1990). *The Design of Everyday Things* (Also published as: *The Psychology of Everyday Things*, 1988, Harper-Collins, New York ed.), Basic Books, Doubleday, New York, NY.
 29. OECD. (2015). *Frascati Manual*, 7th ed, Chapter 2. <http://oe.cd/frascati>
 30. Olechowski, A. L., Eppinger, S. D., Joglekar, N., & Tomaschek, K. (2020). Technology readiness levels: Shortcomings and improvement opportunities. *Systems Engineering*, 23(4), 395–408.
 31. Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health*, 42(5), 533–544.
 32. Petronikolou, V., Petsani, D., Santonen, T., Konstantinidis, E., Vervoort, K., Kehayia, E., & Azevedo, N. (2024). VITALISE D2.7 Standard Version 6. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13736440>
 33. Puerari, E., De Koning, J. I. J. C., Von Wirth, T., Karré, P. M., Mulder, I. J., & Loorbach, D. A. (2018). Co-Creation Dynamics in Urban Living Labs. *Sustainability*, 10(6), 1893. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10061893>
 34. Roy, R., & Warren, J. P. (2019). Card-based design tools: A review and analysis of 155 card decks for designers and designing. *Design Studies*, 63, 125–154.
 35. Santonen, T., Despoina, P., Silia, P., Martina, D., Panagiotis, B., & Evdokimos, K. (2024.) Harmonizing Living Lab Services: Towards consolidated service portfolio. In *Proc. XXXV ISPIM Innovation Conference*, Osaka, Japan.
 36. Schumpeter, J. A., & Swedberg, R. (2021). *The theory of economic development*. Routledge, New York, NY.
 37. Schuurman, D. (2015) *Bridging the Gap Between Open and User Innovation?: Exploring the Value of Living Labs as a Means to Structure User Contribution and Manage Distributed Innovation*. Ph.D. Thesis, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium.
 38. Schuurman, D., De Marez, L., & Ballon, P. (2015). Living Labs: a systematic literature review. In *Open Living Lab Days 2015*, Istanbul, Turkey.
 39. Schuurman, D., Mahr, D., De Marez, L., & Ballon, P. (2013). A fourfold typology of living labs: an empirical investigation amongst the ENoLL community. In *Proc. 2013 International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation (ICE) & IEEE International Technology Management Conference*, pp. 1–11, The Hague, Netherlands.
 40. Simonsen, J., & Robertson, T. (Eds.). (2013). *Routledge international handbook of participatory design*. New York, Routledge.
 41. Ståhlbröst, A. (2008). *Forming future IT: the living lab way of user involvement* (Doctoral dissertation, Luleå Tekniska Universitet).
 42. Ståhlbröst, A. (2013). A living lab as a service: creating value for micro-enterprises through collaboration and innovation. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 3(11), 37–42.
 43. Stickdorn, M., & Schneider, J. (2012). *This is service design thinking: Basics, tools, cases*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey.
 44. Trencher, G. (2019). Towards the smart city 2.0: Empirical evidence of using smartness as a tool for tackling social challenges. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 142, 117–128.
 45. US Department of Energy. <https://www.energy.gov/technologytransitions/mission-0>
 46. Von Geibler, J., Erdmann, L., Liedtke, C., Rohn, H., Stabe, M, Berner, S., ... Kennedy, K. (2014).

Living Labs for Regenerative Futures: Connecting Local and Global Innovation Ecosystems

30 September – 3 October 2025, Andorra la Vella, Andorra

- Exploring the Potential of a German Living Lab Research Infrastructure for the Development of Low Resource Products and Services. *Resources*, 3(3), 575–598. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources3030575>
47. Von Hippel, E. (1986). Lead users: a source of novel product concepts. *Management Science*, 32(7), 791–805.
 48. Voytenko, Y., McCormick, K., Evans, J., & Schliwa, G. (2016). Urban living labs for sustainability and low carbon cities in Europe: Towards a research agenda. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 123, 45–54.
 49. Yasuoka, M., Akasaka, F., Kimura, A., & Ihara, M. (2018) Living labs as a methodology for service design-An analysis based on cases and discussions from a systems approach viewpoint. In *Proc. 15th International Design Conference*, pp. 127–136, Dubrovnik, Croatia.
 50. Yin, R. K. (1994). Discovering the future of the case study, *Method in evaluation research*. *Evaluation Practice*, 15(3), 283–290.
 51. Zomerdijk, L. G., & Voss, C. A. (2010). Service design for experience-centric services. *Journal of Service Research*, 13(1), 67–82.